

AN APPROACH TO KAPHAJ MUKHAPAK THROUGH AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

One of the illnesses brought on Predominant is Mukhpaka which interferes with day-to-day functioning is the inability to eat and speak normally. It can happen anywhere in the mouth, including the tongue, palate, gums, lips, and cheeks. A case presentation about Mukhapaka is shown here. In this instance, sapuya paka took place at the inner mucosa of mouth portion. The patient had been afflicted with the same illnesses for over a year. He took numerous other medications to help it go away, but eventually it flared up again. He receives a full recovery from the illness using the Ayurvedic treatment protocol. No agitation was observed in the subsequent follow-ups.

KEYWORDS: Kaphaj Mukhapak, Stomatitis, Oral ulcers.

INTRODUCTION

The oral cavity plays a vital role in the initial stages of digestion, speech, and overall wellbeing. Any pathology affecting the mouth not only hampers food intake but also disturbs the quality of life. Among these, *Mukhapaka*—commonly known as **oral ulcers or stomatitis**—is a frequently encountered disorder. It is characterized by painful ulcerations, burning sensation, and inflammation of the oral mucosa. From an Ayurvedic perspective, *Mukhapaka* is considered a **Pittaja dominant disorder**, where vitiated Pitta along with Rakta (blood) leads to ulcerative changes in the oral cavity. Also, it is classified into different types according to doshas, like

Vaat, Pitta, Kapha. Though it is Pitta dominant disease but when kapha dosha gets aggravated due to the dietary habits it along with pitta causes kaphaj mukhapak. Improper dietary habits such as excessive intake of sour, spicy, salty, sweet, heavy to digest and piquant food items, along with lifestyle factors like tobacco chewing, smoking, alcohol consumption, and stress, further aggravate the condition. Although mouth ulcers are generally not life-threatening, they are recurrent and troublesome, often interfering with mastication, deglutition, and speech. Ayurveda emphasizes both preventive and curative measures for *Mukhapaka*, highlighting the importance of Shodhana (purificatory therapies), Shamana (palliative therapies), local treatments, Rasayana (rejuvenation), and proper **Ahara-Vihara (dietary-lifestyle regimen)**. Thus, the condition not only requires symptomatic management but also holistic correction of underlying doshic imbalance and lifestyle.

CASE STUDY

A 32 years Male Patient came in OPD with the symptoms of

- Mukhavran (Mouth Ulcer) (Mild)
- Sapuya Mukhapak (Whitish Pus)
- Daha (Burning)
- Dysphagia (Difficulty in swallowing food)
- Asyavairasya (Diminish Taste of food)
- Malavstambh (Constipation) ++
- Chintadhikya

History of Present Illness

Patient was apparently alright 2 years before. Gradually he experienced mukhavran since then. Beginning day number of Mukhavran single with yellow-white red corner, increase in sustainable numbers, gradually it became very frequent. He had undergone many modern treatments still having no relief. Before he had history of taking fast food, spicy, Adhyashan (eating a new meal before the previous one is digested), Ajirnaashan (previous meal is undigested for too long), Etc along with constipation.

H/O- Chickenpox, Piles (2015)

F/H/O- NA

S/H/O- NA

Allergy-NA

AGGRAVATING FACTORS

Excess intake of Spices such as black pepper, long pepper, ginger and chilli.

Poor oral hygiene

General Examination

Bp-120/80 mm/hg

GC -Fair

Pulse-72/min

Spo2-97%

RR-19/min

S/E (Systemic Examination)

RS- AEBE clear

CVS-S1S2 Normal

CNS-Conscious Oriented

Ashtavidha Pareeksha

Nadi-Saam, Sukshma Mand

Mala-Malavstambh, Pichil mala, Visrata

Mutra-Prakrut

Jiva-Sama, shwetabh

Shabd-Mand

Sparsh-Ushna

Druka-Prakrut

Aakruti-Krusha

Colour -White with red corner, Present Pus Filled with mild pain

Number-Multiple in Nature

ORAL CAVITY

Buccal Mucosa :- Whitish patch Present on buccal Mucosa ++

Hard Palate :- whitish

Tongue :- Whitish Patch ++

NIDAN PANCHAK**Hetu-**

- **Ahara-** Guru anna, Adhyshan, Ajirnanashan, Viruddha ahar.

- **Vihara-** Avyayam, Jagran, Chintan, Atinidra.

Samprapti

Samprapti Ghatak

Dosha- Kapha pradhan, Pitta-vatanubandhi

Dushya- Rasa, Mansa,

Srotodushti- Annavaha, Rasavaha,

Vyadhi Avastha- Saam, Kapha utleksh, Dosha urdhva gati

Sadhyasadhyatwa- Sukhsadhya

Vyadhi marg- Abhyantar

Vyadhi nidan- Kpaha Pradhan Mukhapak

Chikitsa

Shamana Chikitsa

Date	Symptoms	Name of Kalpa	Matra	Aushadi kala (Frequency)	Anupana
15/06/2025	S Puya Mukhapak (Whitish Pus) -Daha (Burning) -Difficult to swallow food -Asyavairasya (Diminish Taste of food)	1) Aaragwadh churna 2) Trifala, Yashti, Nimb 3) Arogya-Wardhini vati 4) Gandush (Yashti, Nimb, Mahasudarshan churn)	250 mg 125mg 2 vati 200ml	BD BD BD OD	Luke warm water Honey Luke warm water

	-Mukhavran (Mouth Ulcer) (Mild) -Malavstambh (Constipation) ++ -Chintadhikya++				Kwath
26/06/2025	S Puya Mukhapak (Whitish Pus) -Daha (Burning) -Difficult to engulfed food -Asyavairasya (Diminish Taste of food) -Mukhavran (Mouth Ulcer) (Mild) -Malavstambh (Constipation) -Chintadhikya+ Upashay 50%	Same as above Add Mahatiktak ghrut			
11/07/2025	S Puya Mukhapak (Whitish Pus) -Daha (Burning) -Difficult to engulfed food -Asyavairasya (Diminish Taste of food) -Mukhavran (Mouth Ulcer) (Mild) -Malavstambh (Constipation) Upshaya 80%	Same as above			
25/07/2025	Upshaya 90%	Advice Panchkarma, vaman			

DISCUSSION

Kaphaj Mukhapak can be readily and successfully treated with the right course of action and some of the ayurvedic medications mentioned. Since we must be specific about whether it is Vataj, Pitaja, or Kaphaj, it requires a proper diagnosis.

Aragwadha: It has blood purifying, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties, which help cleanse the oral cavity, reduce burning sensation, and promote healing of mouth ulcers and inflammation. It remove pus by its lekhana guna.

Trifala

- 1) Amalaki:- Aamalaki is high in antioxidants and vitamin C and is frequently used in Ayurveda to regulate the Pitta dosha, which is linked to the body's metabolism and heat.
- 2) Bibhitaki:- People who frequently get colds, coughs, or other respiratory problems can benefit from it since it helps cleanse the liver and respiratory system. Bibhitaki is beneficial for those who suffer from constipation or irregular bowel movements because it also promotes good digestion and excretion.
- 3) Haritaki:- Haritaki has ability to balance all tree doshas

Yashti:- Yashtimadhu's Madhur Rasa (sweet taste) and Sheeta Virya (cooling properties) help to calm vitiated Pitta and Rakta Dosha (blood diseases). It has pacifying (Sharmana) and healing (Ropana) properties that improve oral hygiene, lessen discomfort, ulceration, and salivation, and hasten the healing process.

Nimb:- Because of its anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and wound-healing qualities as well as its tikta (bitter) taste, neem (Nimba) helps treat mukhapaka (stomatitis). It reduces inflammation and encourages the healing of oral lesions and ulcers by calming the Pitta dosha, which is frequently the cause of oral lesions. Neem can be used as a paste for topical application or in decoctions for gargling (gandoosh or kavalagraha), either by itself or in combination with other healthful components.

Arogyawarddhini vati:- Aarogyawardhini helps in management of indigestion by digesting the aam due to its deepan and pachan properties, it also helps in pachan of saam kapha and elimination of the excessive kapha and pitta doshas.

Mahatiktak ghrit:- Reduces the Tikshna & ushna guna of pitta.

SAMPRAPTI BHNAGA

CONCLUSION

This case report highlights the clinical relevance of classical Ayurvedic formulations and personalized treatment protocols in managing functional oral disorders. It also highlights the efficacy of Ayurvedic management in treating kaphaj mukhpak, a condition primarily caused by vitiation of kaphaj dosha (along with Pitta Dosha) and impairment of Agni (digestive fire). The therapeutic approach focused on Deepana and Pachana to restore Agni, along with Pitta-shamana, Kaphaghna, and Srotoshodhana interventions to correct the underlying pathophysiology. Significant symptomatic relief was observed in complaints like s puya (pus filled), daha (burning), and Aruchi (loss of appetite), without adverse effects.

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